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Polarographic Studies on the Reaction Between Manganese Sulphate and Sodium Mandelate

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It has been found that mandelic acid forms 1:1 chelates with number of metals¹⁻⁴ due to liberation of hydroxy as well as carboxylic protons of mandelic acid.

Polarographic studies of manganese (II) complexes with some ligands have been done⁵⁻⁶. Studies on Mn(II)-mandelate complex are reported here.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of Analar quality and the solutions were prepared by using double distilled water. The polarograms were recorded on Tinsley pen recording polarograph. The pH values of each set was determined by Philips pH meter. All the operations were done at room temperature.

The experimental solutions were made keeping potassium chloride, manganese sulphate and gelatin concentrations constant at 1M, 0.00125M and 0.001% respectively and the ligand (sodium-mandelate) concentration was varied up to 0.01125 M.

The polarograms of these samples were recorded after keeping the sets of solutions for 24 hr. and deoxygenating each set by passing purified hydrogen.

The half-wave potential $E_{1/2}$ of each polarogram was determined⁷, and then the change in half-wave potential $\Delta E_{1/2}$ with change in ligand concentration was plotted against $\Delta \log C_x$ (logarithm of change in ligand concentration). The number of ligand ions (P) that are co-ordinated with one metal ion was calculated using the following relation⁸.

$$\frac{\Delta E_{1/2}}{\Delta \log C_x} = -0.0591 \frac{P}{n}$$

and then the dissociation constant⁹ of the complex species by the following relation

$$(E_{1/2})_0 - (E_{1/2})_a = \frac{0.0591}{n} \log K_c - \frac{0.0591}{n} p \log C_x$$

The reversibility of the electrode reaction was verified by plotting $\log \frac{i_d - i}{i}$ against the corresponding potential

E where i_d = diffusion current and i = current at any applied potential E.

The plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ Vs $\Delta \log C_x$ for experimental data gives a straight line, the value of p was calculated and was found to be equal to one, indicating the formation of a 1:1 Mn(II)-mandelate complex. The value of the formation constant, K, is 1×10^4 (30° and $\mu = 1.0055$ to 1.055).

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Enthalpimetric Studies of Some Beryllium Complexes*

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CALORIMETRY provides a means for the direct measurement of enthalpy changes involved in complex forming reactions. Heat of reaction data for many metal ligand systems have been obtained from $\ln K$ vs $1/T$ plots (using sometimes only two temperatures). These are often of questionable validity since variations of $\ln K$ with temperature, in the intervals normally employed, are of the same order of magnitude as the uncertainties in the measurement of $\ln K$. Since, ΔH and not ΔG is a true measure of the metal ligand bond strength, the availability of reliable enthalpy values would lead to a better understanding of the factors affecting the strength of these bonds. The present paper describes the calorimetric measurement of enthalpy changes during the complexation of Be^{2+} with oxalate and malonate ions.

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Experimental

The calorimetric set up was similar to that used by Athavale *et al*¹. It was calibrated using a heater made of manganin wire ($R=15\Omega$) and connected through a time-relay circuit. The sensing element was a 2 K Ω thermistor and the off-balance potential was observed on a 10 mv. Honeywell Brown 153 $\times$ 18 recorder. The sensitivity obtained was 0.003 $^\circ$ /recorder division. ΔH for nitric acid-sodium hydroxide neutralisation agreed with the reported literature value.

Reagents

1. 1 M beryllium solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount of B. D. H. Anala R $\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ in acidified distilled water.

2. 1 M potassium malonate solution was prepared by neutralising to a pH of 8.5-9.0 a solution containing the required amount of purified malonic acid with Analar potassium hydroxide. The malonic acid was purified by recrystallisation from a solution in ether-benzene mixture (1:1) containing 5% petroleum ether and drying in vacuum.

3. 1 M potassium oxalate prepared as above using B. D. H. Analar oxalic acid instead of malonic acid.

The relevant experimental conditions and thermodynamic data obtained are summarised in Table 1. The final pH value of the solutions was between 5-7. This ensured the complete and exclusive formation of the dioxalate and di-malonate.

Results and Discussion

The measured heat changes ΔH_0 result from the replacement of the hydration sheath around the metal ion by the ligand atoms while the bond strength of interest between the metal ion and the ligand refers to the enthalpy change (ΔH_i) of the gas phase reaction. The latter is related to the former through (among other things) the heat of hydration of the metal ion². For the present case, where the interaction of the same metal ion with closely related ligands is considered, ΔH_0 values would directly reflect the relative bond strengths of the metal with the two ligating structures.

Our investigations on the stabilities of beryllium complexes with a large number of oxygen donor ligands led us to believe that the lower stabilities of Be^{2+} complexes with ligands leading to five membered ring structures as against those forming six membered rings were due to unfavourable enthalpy changes caused by a steric effect³. The small Be^{2+} ion (ionic radius $\sim 0.31\text{\AA}$) probably fits more snugly in a six membered ring than in a five membered ring structure wherein the bonding oxygen atoms are further apart. The enthalpy and entropy changes obtained in the present investigation support this assumption. The entropy changes during complexation with oxalate and malonate ions are of the same order of magnitude. The enthalpy changes in both cases are positive as has been observed with carboxylate ligands⁴ but significantly enough, ΔH_0 for oxalate ions is much more endothermic than that for malonate indicating a definite ring strain in the former case.

TABLE 1

a) Enthalpy values for Be^{2+} Complexes

	Be ²⁺ Soln. Conc ^a mM	pH	Ligand Soln Conc ^a mM	pH	Final pH Beryllium dimalonate	ΔH_i (Corrected for Blank) KCl mole	
1	1.00	3.50	4.00	8.60	6.60	3.30	Mean 3.3
2	2.00	3.35	8.00	8.60	6.60	3.27	
3	1.00	3.50	4.00	8.50	6.45	3.26	
Beryllium dioxalate							
1	1.00	3.50	4.00	8.80	5.40	8.34	8.1
2	0.50	3.80	3.00	8.80	5.60	8.20	
3	1.00	3.50	3.00	8.80	5.20	7.70	

b) Thermodynamic functions for Be^{2+} complexes

		$\log \beta_2^{\circ}$	ΔF KCal/mole	ΔH	ΔS (esu)
1	Be (Mal) ₂	8.50	-11.73	3.28	50
2	Be (Ox) ₂	5.91	- 8.14	8.08	54

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Chalcones. XVIII : Potential Germicides Derived from Hydroxy Acetonaphthones

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CHALCONES have variable germicidal¹⁻⁷, bactericidal,^{1,19,20} fungicidal¹¹ and carcinogenic¹² activity. These effects may be either due to interaction with the germs under investigation or for killing bacterias by inhibiting the supporting microorganisms or by direct action. Moreover, methoxy and hydroxy chalcones²¹ can check up the destruction of adrenaline. Furthermore, naphthyl and phenanthryl chalcones possess potential bactericidal and carcinogenic²² activity. Considering these facts various hydroxy naphthyl and nitro hydroxy naphthyl chalcones have been synthesised expecting enhanced germicidal effect. The present communication is in pursuit of our work⁴⁻⁸ on syntheses of naphthyl chalcones of biochemical importance.

4-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone and 4-hydroxy-3-nitro-1-aceto-naphthone have been condensed in presence of 10% alcoholic caustic potash solution with various aryl aldehydes to form compounds of the type (I) and (II).

Type (I) R=H and R'=H ; 2-,3-,4-Cl ; 2-,3-,4-Me ; and 2-,3-,4-NO₂.

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Type (II) R=NO₂ and R'=5-Br-2-OH ; 2-Me ; 5-Br-3:4-(OCH₃)₂ and 5:6-benzo.

The condensation of 4-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone and 4-hydroxy-3-nitro-1-acetonaphthone with chloro, bromo, methyl and methoxy benzaldehydes were obtained in good yields at room temperature within 24-50 hr. The interaction with nitrobenzaldehydes under the same conditions gave dark coloured products of unknown composition. The same reaction when carried at 10°-15° gave yellow coloured crystalline compounds in 75-80% yield. This abnormal behaviour of nitrobenzaldehydes may be due to its sensitiveness towards alkali solution at elevated temperatures.

The compounds were characterised by the vivid colours obtained on wetting with conc. sulfuric acid, elemental analyses, and by preparing a few 2:4-DNPs. The elemental analyses for C, H, and N for synthesised compounds were within ±0.5% of the calculated value.

Pharmacology

The agar-cup method was used to investigate germicidal activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* of the synthesised chalcones. The inocula were obtained from agar solidified nutrient broth media and growth was checked at (32°±2°) after 24 hr. None of the compounds described in this paper were found to be significantly active at a concentration of 100±15 μg ml.

Experimental

*Preparation of 4-hydroxy-3-nitro-1-acetonaphthone*²⁵ : It was prepared by the nitration of 4-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone²⁸ in glacial acetic acid.

Preparation of Naphthyl chalcones - Naphthyl chalcone analogues were obtained by dropwise mixing 10% caustic potash solution (10 to 15 ml.) to an equimolar aldehyde free alcoholic solution of the required naphthyl ketone and aryl aldehydes at low temperature with constant stirring. The dark coloured reaction mixture on keeping at room temperature deposited crude compound. It was collected and crystallised from alcohol. The final purity was checked by thin layer chromatography.¹⁸

2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives were prepared by grinding the ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution of the required compound with the reagent at 100° and orange to red coloured derivatives were collected and purified from ethyl acetate unless otherwise mentioned (Table 1). The derivatives were analysed satisfactorily for nitrogen.